

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MAMMOGRAPHIC FEATURES IN THE STAGES OF BREAST CANCER

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Abstract

This study will be examining mammographic imaging across four stages of breast cancer. In reviewing mammographic characteristics of the masses as either oval or round, in addition to the margins, shape, density, and / or the presence of microcalcifications, the focus aims to identify imaging features associated with each stage of the breast cancer. The research will also examine associations between imaging features and tumor progression. The results found clear mammographic patterns for each stage of cancer. The results of this study will enhance diagnosis processes and diagnostic support to the radiologists in identifying malignant breast tumor in early stage of the cancer.

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INTRODUCTION

Breast Cancer:

Breast cancer is among the frequent prevalent cancer experienced by female in general. Breast cancer occurs where malignant cells multiply uncontrollably in the breast and form tumors. Its originates in breast tissues, most often in the cell's linings the milk ducts (ductal carcinoma) or less in the lobules that produce milk for the ducts (lobular carcinoma). About 80% of the breast cancers are to referred as invasive cancer in the sense that they can spread out of the breast and affect other regions of the body [1].

Breast cancer rank as a second leading cause of cancer related death globally, resulting in around 685,000

fatalities each year [2]. Pakistan, the fourth most populous nation in Asia and among the five countries that together make up 75% of the continent's population. In Pakistan, approximately 1 out of every 5 Pakistan women may develop breast cancer at some point in life which is highest risk level reported in Asia. More than 90,000 women are diagnosed with disease each year. Around 40,000 women die from breast cancer in Pakistan annually [3]. In 2020, breast cancer represented 28.7% of all newly diagnosed cancers (25,928 cases) and was responsible for 11.7% of total cancer-related deaths (13,725 deaths) [4].

Figure 1.1 In Pakistan various type of cancer were prevalent in 2020, with breast cancer showing the highest incidence [4].

1.2 Mammography

is a specialized X-ray imaging technique that uses a low dose of radiation to visualize breast tissue, and resultant image is mammogram. Mammography helps to detect and diagnose breast disease in patient earlier [5]. Radiation exposure in mammography is minimal, ranging from 1.5 to 4mGy. Tumors appear on mammography as high density masses with irregular or radiating edges [6]. Mammography is known for its high sensitivity, specificity, negative predictive value, consistency, and ease of use—especially in women with fatty breast tissue. For this reason, the World Health Organization (WHO) advises women to receive routine mammographic screening [7]. Mammography began nearly 100 years

ago when German surgeon Dr. Albert Salomon used X-rays on the mastectomy sample and observed the difference between cancerous and healthy tissues. Identifying tumors in the breast was challenging at the time because breast tissue differ from person to person, and early imaging technique produced low quality images [8]. Three recent advances in mammography include digital mammography, computer-aided detection and breast tomosynthesis. **Standard Mammographic view** Standard views used in mammography are bilateral craniocaudal (CC) is above the breast and mediolateral oblique (MLO) is at an angled position.

Figure 1.2 Standard views (a) the mediolateral oblique view, taken from the side at an angle, and (b) the craniocaudal view, taken from above the breast looking downward[9].

1.4 Risk Factor for breast cancer:

Age has strong influence on occurrence of breast cancer. Women aged 40 and above are more frequently affected. Research shows that those who experience menopause later—at 55 years or older—face a higher risk compared to women whose menopause begins around age 45 [10]. Higher breast tissue density with an increased risk of breast cancer and this pattern is seen in both premenopausal and postmenopausal women [11]. Vitamin D deficiency can cause the conversion of non-metastatic cells to metastatic cells. In Pakistan approximately one in three women is affected by vitamin D deficiency. Physical inactivity is related to breast cancer, largely because it increases obesity which is major in many diseases [11]. World obesity observation shows a national obesity risk of 6.5/10 in Pakistan. Few studies have investigated why cancer screening and

treatment are delayed in Pakistan, pointing to low awareness, socioeconomic barriers, limited access and affordability, and exposure to harmful industrial chemicals [12].

1.5 Breast Cancer Stages

Once the person gets their breast cancer diagnosis, the doctor will work to determine if the cancer has spread to other parts of the body, and if so, how far. This process is called staging. The stage of a cancer describes how much cancer is found in the body [13]. The earliest breast cancers are classified as stage 0 (carcinoma in situ). After that, stages progress from I (1) to IV (4). For breast cancer, to find out stage of cancer that is used most frequently is the According to the current AJCC TNM system starting from January 2018, both clinical and pathologic staging are used to classify breast cancer [14].

Figure 3. Breast Cancer Stages at which patients first presented for medical evaluation [15].

1.6 Details of TNM Staging System

In breast cancer staging, the letter T followed by a number from 1 to 4 describes the size of the primary tumor. The letter N, combined with a number from 1 to 3, indicates whether cancer has spread to nearby lymph nodes and how many are involved. The letter M, followed by either 0 or 1, shows whether the cancer has metastasized (spread) to distant parts of the body, such as the lungs, liver, or bones [16]. Over 70% of breast cancer cases in Pakistan are identified only at stage III or IV. A study from the institute of the Nuclear Medicine & Oncology in Lahore found that 64% of breast cancer were in advanced stage with the mean patient age being 46.5 ± 13 years. Among the patient 47% were diagnosed in stage 2, 36% at stage 3, 2% at stage 4. In comparison with other local studies have documented stage 4 disease in 17% to 25% of cases [17].

Material and Methodology

Participants will be women between 28 and 65 years of age. Eligibility requirements specify that women must be 25 to 65 years old, have a confirmed breast cancer diagnosed. Essential patient details will be collected, including age, tumor features (such as size and anatomical position), histopathological classification, and any pertinent medical background.

2.1 Mammography protocols:

A mammography examination was performed using a Toshiba Metal Tronica system. The tube voltage was set to 25 KVp and the tube current to 250 mAs,

with exposure time adjusted according to breast thickness and density. Four 24×30 cm cassettes were used—two for the mediolateral oblique (MLO) views and two for the craniocaudal (CC) views. Compression size ranges from 10 kg to 20 kg. The procedure’s effective dose, 2.7 mSv or less than 3.0 mSv, is comparable to the amount of natural background radiation received over roughly seven weeks.

3. Results and discussion

In figure 3.1 shows mammographic CC and MLO views of a 37 years old female patient. The left breast shows a well-defined cystic-appearing lesion without any suspicious calcifications or distortion. The imaging characteristics suggest a probably benign finding and are classified as BI-RADS III. These features are consistent with a benign cyst, for which short-interval follow-up is typically advised.

Figure 3.1 left breast CC & MLO view shows a cyst lesion likely benign (BIRADs III).

In figure 3.2, the mammographic CC and MLO views of the right breast in this 80-year-old patient demonstrate a focal asymmetry with an irregular nodular density measuring approximately 1.37 × 1.74 inches. The overall imaging appearance suggests mild suspicion and is categorized as BI-RADS 4A,

which corresponds to an early-suspicious stage (Stage 4A clinically). Given these characteristics, targeted ultrasound and biopsy are recommended for definitive assessment. These findings highlight the importance of correlating imaging features with clinical evaluation for accurate diagnosis.

Figure 3.2: A focal asymmetry / irregular nodular density is identified. Lesion measure 1.37x 1.74 inches (Category 4A).

Figure 3.3 shows mammographic evaluation of the left breast in this 48-year-old patient shows a well-circumscribed, round to oval mass located in the upper outer quadrant, measuring approximately 1.87

× 1.35 inches. The lesion demonstrates smooth margins and uniform density, consistent with a simple breast cyst or lipoma. Based on imaging appearance, the case is categorized as BI-RADS 2 (benign).

Figure 3. 3: A well circumscribed, round to oval mass is seen in the upper outer quadrant of left breast measuring 1.87x 1.35 inches. Simple breast cyst /lipoma in left breast.

Figure 3.4 shows mammographic views of right breast CC & MLO of 42 years old female patient. The right breast mammogram (CC and MLO views) shows a well-defined rounded soft-tissue mass in the

lower region, measuring approximately 0.81 inches (~2 cm). A few coarse benign-appearing calcifications are also noted around the lesion. No associated architectural distortion or suspicious clustered microcalcifications are seen.

Figure 3.4, shows the (a) Left breast CC and MLO views showing normal parenchymal appearance (b) Right breast CC and MLO views demonstrating a well-defined rounded mass in the lower region measuring approximately 0.81 inches (~2 cm).

Figure 3.5, shows the mammographic CC and MLO views of left breast of a 52 years old female patient. The left breast mammogram (CC and MLO views) demonstrates a high-density, irregularly

marginated mass in the upper region, more conspicuous on the MLO view. The lesion shows spiculated/ill-defined borders, raising suspicion for an invasive process.

Figure 3.5. CC & MLO views of left breast.

Conclusion

The mammographic evaluation of the presented cases revealed a spectrum of findings ranging from normal dense breast patterns to suspicious irregular masses. Well-defined rounded lesions were more suggestive of benign changes, whereas ill-defined or speculated masses showed features concerning for malignancy. In several cases, the imaging characteristics were significant enough to suggest the need for further evaluation with biopsy for definitive diagnosis. These observations highlight the importance of correlating mammographic features with clinical assessment to ensure timely detection of breast pathology. Overall, the study reinforces the critical role of mammography in early diagnosis and decision-making for appropriate patient management.

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